

Using a spatial statistical model to explore voting behaviour in the UK 2019 general election

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Summary

This paper examines aggregated voting behaviour in the 2019 UK general election using a hierarchical spatial autoregressive model (HSAM). Such a model aims to simultaneously measure two sources of spatial variation. The first is that due to a spatial unit's position within a nested structure of administrative boundaries which are hypothesised as relevant a priori. The second is a type of spatial effect owing to the influence of neighbouring constituencies represented by an intrinsic conditional autoregressive (ICAR) component. The results show varying associations between census profile and voting behaviour at different levels and in different parts of England and Wales.

KEYWORDS: spatial regression, hierarchical model, ICAR, UK general election 2019, Butler swing

1 Introduction

When choosing how to vote, many factors will affect that decision and it is reasonable to hypothesise that there would be spatial processes at play in addition to differences which might be associated with socio-economic factors alone. Constituencies with similar types of census profile but in different locations do not necessarily produce similar election results. We further suspect that these spatial processes might occur in the form of both a '*vertical*' hierarchical process and lowest level '*horizontal*' neighbourhood effect. Dorling (2010) has described how UK society has become ever more geographically fragmented since the 1970s. If the symptoms of this were a factor in voting allegiance, we could expect a spatial hierarchical structure to pick up on this. It is also well-established that voter behaviour is often subject to a neighbourhood effect, which Pattie and Johnston (2000) summarised with the phrase "people who talk together vote together". The presence of such an

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effect would take the form of positive spatial autocorrelation among neighbouring constituencies. This paper seeks to examine these variations using what Dong and Harris (2015) refer to as HSAM.

2 Data

The census (2011) and voting data for this model were obtained from the `parlitoools` R package (Odell, 2020). The measure of voter behaviour which the paper models is the Butler Swing (Butler & Van Beek, 1990) to the Conservative Party from Labour in England and Wales. The other parts of the UK were excluded as they have a very different profile of competing parties. This metric is a staple of televised election coverage and is calculated as the mean of the difference between Conservative percentage points gain and Labour loss. It was positive in the vast majority of constituencies in the study area (Figure 1).

Three explanatory variables (see Table 1), normalised as Z-scores for the model, were chosen from those proposed by Beecham et al. (2018) in their examination of spatial variation of voter behaviour in the 2016 Brexit referendum (values shown in Figure 2).

Table 1: Description of explanatory variables

Explanatory variable	Calculation from 2011 census	Justification/theory
degree educated	percentage of population with level 4 qualification or higher	post-industrial / knowledge-economy / peripherality
health not good	percentage of population self-reporting ‘fair’, ‘bad’, or ‘very bad’ health	life outcomes / young people
white	percentage of population of white ethnicity	ethnic / cultural diversity / values

3 Model

Our proposed model has random slopes and intercepts at the region and county levels. Below these, the constituency component could be calibrated as spatially correlated random intercepts, spatially correlated random slopes, or both.

These three formulations were considered, and their performance metrics are shown in Table 2.

Figure 1: (L) Butler swing to the Conservatives. Figures projected as Dougenik cartograms such that equal populations occupy equal area while maintaining constituency contiguities. (R) Swingometer for each region.

Figure 2: Values of independent variables.

Table 2: Comparison of models

Model	Constituency-level autoregressive spatial process(es)	AIC	RMSE	adjR2	Loglik
1	ICAR varying intercept	2336	1.43	0.76	-1015
2	ICAR varying coefficients	2373	1.62	0.73	-1086
3	ICAR varying intercept + varying coefficients	2381	1.64	0.73	-1094

Model 1 performed best under all metrics and this is the model which we now discuss. Its lowest level ICAR component can be interpreted as random constituency-specific effects which account for further differences in voting behaviour which are not associated with the chosen census variables, nor with location within a region or county. Instead, they have a pattern consistent with a neighbourhood effect.

The structure of the optimal model is shown as Equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_{ijk} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{degree}_{ijk} + \beta_2 \text{health}_{ijk} + \beta_3 \text{white}_{ijk} \\
 & + b_{0i} + b_{1i} \text{degree}_{ijk} + b_{2i} \text{health}_{ijk} + b_{3i} \text{white}_{ijk} \\
 & + b_{0ij} + b_{1ij} \text{degree}_{ijk} + b_{2ij} \text{health}_{ijk} + b_{3ij} \text{white}_{ijk} \\
 & + \gamma_l \\
 & + \epsilon_{ijk}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where y_{ijk} is the swing in constituency k in county j in region i for

- $i = 1, \dots, 11$ regions,
- $j = 1, \dots, J_i$ counties within region i ,
- $k = 1, \dots, K_{ij}$ constituencies within county j within region i , and
- $l = m = 1, \dots, 571$ individual constituencies,
- with $\epsilon_{ijk} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$.

The β 's and b 's are fixed and random effects respectively, and the γ_l 's are lowest level constituency random effects with ICAR distribution:

$$\gamma_l | \gamma_m, m \neq l \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\frac{1}{\sum_m w_{lm}} \sum_m w_{lm} \gamma_m, \frac{\sigma_l^2}{\sum_m w_{lm}} \right) \tag{2}$$

where w_{lm} is the element of a binary spatial weights matrix \mathbf{W} corresponding to row l and column

m , where

$$w_{lm} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if constituencies } l \text{ and } m \text{ are adjacent,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Equation 2 implies that the conditional expectation of the autoregressive component, γ_l , for any constituency is the mean of that of its neighbouring constituencies, with a decreasing variance as the count of neighbours increases. To overcome the problem of unidentifiability, the constraint $\sum_L \gamma_l = 0$ is added to centre the model.

Rather than using the standard hierarchical modelling packages in R (such as `lme4` or `nmle`), which do not have the functionality to implement ICAR components, an equivalent model was instead implemented as a Generalised Additive Model (GAM) using the `mgcv` package (Wood, 2011). `mgcv` can implement hierarchical effects due to an equivalence between the shrinkage which occurs in multilevel modelling and the penalty imposed against wiggleness (lack of smoothness) in a penalised GAM. The use of GAMs to capture *continuous* spatial effects using Gaussian Process splines was demonstrated by Comber et al. (2024) in the context of the 2016 Brexit referendum. Analogously, this model uses Markov Random Field (MRF) splines to model *discrete* ICAR spatial effects across areal units.

4 Results

4.1 Global effects

Figure 3 shows that at mean levels of education, health and ethnic diversity, the global mean swing to the Conservatives was just over 4%. An increase of one standard deviation in percentage of ‘degree educated’ is associated with a reduction of 2.1 in swing, while a similar increase in ‘white’ is associated with an further increase of 1.052 in swing. The ‘health not good’ covariate is not significant at the 95% level although there is a suggestion that it is positive.

Figure 3: Fixed or global intercept and coefficients.

4.2 Variance

The estimates shown in Table 3 can be seen as analogous to an *analysis of variance* for different causes of spatial variability. 18.5% of total variance occurs at the region level, with 8.9% at county level for a total of 27.4%. The constituency level neighbourhood effects account for 41.3%. Variations at the region level occur in the slope coefficients for ‘health’ and ‘white’, but not for ‘degree’. However, ‘degree’ does vary at county level, with further variation for ‘white’.

Table 3: Variance explained by model, with associated measures of significance, at different levels and for different spatial processes.

	Variance	Variance %	Cumulative variance %	F test p-value	
Region					
$\sigma^2_{region,int}$	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.074	.
$\sigma^2_{region,degree}$	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.344	
$\sigma^2_{region,health}$	0.63	7.2	7.2	<0.001	***
$\sigma^2_{region,white}$	0.99	11.2	18.5	0.001	***
County					
$\sigma^2_{county,intercept}$	<0.01	<0.01	18.5	0.082	.
$\sigma^2_{county,degree}$	0.44	5.0	23.5	<0.001	***
$\sigma^2_{county,health}$	<0.01	<0.01	23.5	0.540	
$\sigma^2_{county,white}$	0.34	3.9	27.4	0.045	*
Constituency					
$\sigma^2_{constituency,ICAR}$	3.36	41.3	68.7	<0.001	***
Residuals					
σ^2	2.74	31.3	100		

Signif. codes: 0 ‘***’ 0.001 ‘**’ 0.01 ‘*’ 0.05 ‘.’ 0.1 ‘.’ 1

4.3 Region random effects

Looking at the best linear unbiased predictors for each of these random effects in Figure 4, we see that, depending on location, they change the magnitude and, sometimes, the direction of the overall association. Parts of the South East and Merseyside have large enough random effects to alter the direction of association with ‘health not good’, while for the East & West Midlands the effect is strengthened. Similarly, the association of ‘white’ is reinforced in the North East and Yorkshire and The Humber but largely neutralised for London and Merseyside.

4.4 County random effects

Moving to county level, Figure 5 shows the county random effects for ‘degree’. These, however, are not sufficient in any location to alter the direction of the association. The strength is, however, greatly reduced in London, Merseyside, and some counties in the East region, notably Cambridgeshire and Hertfordshire.

Looking at the county random effects of ‘white’ in Figure 6, they are not sufficient to change overall directions but do change magnitudes.

Figure 4: Random effects at region level (insignificant for degree educated).

4.5 Constituency ICAR effects

Finally, the autoregressive component at constituency level is shown in Figure 7. It shows patterns which are largely consistent with administrative boundaries although notable effects which straddle borders are pointed out with red circles. These occur between the East Midlands and Yorkshire and The Humber, and also between the East & West Midlands.

5 Conclusions

This paper shows that a HSAM can be implemented as a GAM to investigate spatial processes. It can be applied to any situation where we suspect that there may be a combination of hierarchically structured and neighbourhood effects occurring simultaneously. Further ideas and detail related to the work presented here can be found in Horan et al. (2024).

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County (within region)

degree_educated (\hat{b}_{1ij})

Figure 5: Random effects of 'degree educated' variable at the county level.

County (within region)

white (\hat{b}_{3ij})

Figure 6: Random effects of 'white' variable at the county level of England and Wales.

Figure 7: The ICAR constituency component at the lowest level. It shows a blue area of increased tendency to swing to the Conservative party, surrounded by a paler band, and red areas to the south, west and parts of the north where the tendency is to swing to Labour, controlling for the covariates and hierarchical effects. Areas of clear cross-regional spillover of effects are highlighted with red circles.

Biographies

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